

Synthesis of a New Series of Furyl and Thienyl substituted Pyrazolines Starting with Furyl and Thienyl Chalcones

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Fourteen heterocyclic furyl and thienyl chalcones (5) were prepared, analysed and converted into the 2-pyrazolines (6) through treatment with hydrazine or methylhydrazine in ethanol or glacial acetic acid solvent. A total of thirty new furyl and thienyl substituted-2-pyrazolines (11a-f, 12a-f, 13a-f, 14a-e 15a-g) were thus prepared and characterised through elemental and spectroscopic measurements. Mechanistic interpretation of the results is also included

PYRAZOLINE derivatives constitute an interesting class of organic compounds with diverse chemical and pharmacological applications¹. For long, it has been recognised that pyrazolines could be synthesised through the interaction of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds with hydrazine or substituted hydrazines². Using this fairly accessible route, workers including one of us³ managed to convert 2,6-diarylidencyclohexanones (1) and ferrocenyl-chalcones (3) into pyrazolines 2 and 4, respectively.

In extension, we present here the preparation of a new series of 2-furyl- and 2-thienylpyrazolines (6) starting with 2-furyl- and 2-thienylchalcones (5).

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a digital Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained with a Zeiss IMT6

infrarot spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) at 90 MHz on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Finnigan MAT 1020 GC/MS instrument. Elemental microanalyses were performed at King Abdulaziz University with a Perkin-Elmer 240-B elemental analyser. Samples for microanalysis were purified by recrystallisation or, for oils, rechromatography with extensive drying of the sample under vacuum. Starting chemicals were obtained from Fluka, BDH, Aldrich or BolaB.

1-(2-Furyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (8a-g) and 1-(2-thienyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (10a-g). General procedure: A mixture of 2-acetyl-furan (or 2-acetyl-thiophene) (0.02 mol), aromatic aldehyde (0.02 mol) and 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide (10 ml) in ethanol (30 ml) was stirred at room temperature for about 2 h. The resulting solid was washed, dried and crystallised from proper solvent (Table 1): 10c *m/z* (rel. int.) 244 (80%, M⁺), 213 (30%, M⁺-CH₃O), 161 (25%, M⁺-C₄H₃S), 133 (M⁺-C₆H₃SO), 111 (75%, C₆H₃O⁺) and 83 (C₄H₃S⁺).

5-Aryl-3-(2-furyl)-2-pyrazolines (11a-f) and 5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines (12a-f) from furyl chalcones (8a-c, g) and thienyl chalcones (10a-f). General procedure: A solution of the respective furyl (or thienyl) chalcone (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and kept at 0° overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent (Table 2). The ¹H nmr spectra of 11c, 11d, 11e and 12d are described in Table 3; 11d *m/z* (rel. int.) 257 (100%, M⁺), 22 (12%, M⁺-NO₂), 135 (72%, M⁺-C₆H₄NO₂), 68 (C₃H₄N₂⁺) and 67 (C₄H₃O⁺); 12d *m/z* (rel. int.) 273 (100%, M⁺), 266 (10%, M⁺-HNO₂) and 151 (73%, -C₆H₄NO₂).

1-Acetyl-5-aryl-3-(2-furyl)-2-pyrazolines (13a-f) from furyl chalcones (8a-e, g). General procedure: A solution of the respective chalcone (0.02 mol) and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF CHALCONES (8a-g, 10a-g)*

Compd. no.	Ar	Yield %	M.p.** (lit. M.p.) °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
8a	C ₆ H ₅	68	88 (88) ^a	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂	3 080, 3 020, 2 980, 2 940, 1 660, 1 610, 1 570
8b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	71	113	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂	3 120, 2 920, 2 840, 1 650, 1 600, 1 560
8c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	75	85 (83) ^a	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂	3 120, 3 110, 3 010, 2 980, 2 840, 1 660, 1 600, 1 570
8d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	89	238 (228) ^a	C ₁₃ H ₈ NO ₄	3 140, 3 120, 2 840, 1 660, 1 600, 1 570
8e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	85	145	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClO ₂	3 140, 3 110, 2 930, 1 660, 1 610, 1 570
8f	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ CH ₃ ⁻ -3,4	67	133	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄	3 140, 3 000, 2 920, 1 660, 1 610, 1 570, 1 465
8g	2-(C ₄ H ₉ S)	72	83 (82.5) ^b	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ S	3 140, 3 120, 1 650, 1 600, 1 560, 1 430
10a	C ₆ H ₅	72	78 (81-2) ^c	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ OS	3 090, 3 040, 2 980, 2 880, 1 660, 1 610, 1 440
10b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	75	142	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ OS	3 090, 2 920, 1 650, 1 600, 1 515
10c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	78	82 (82) ^d	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ S	3 090, 2 840, 1 650, 1 600, 1 514
10d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	88	220 (220) ^e	C ₁₃ H ₈ NO ₂ S	3 110, 2 940, 1 650, 1 600, 1 514
10e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	85	138 (133.5) ^c	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClOS	3 090, 2 850, 1 650, 2 840, 1 514
10f	C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ - <i>p</i>	64	112	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ NOS	3 120, 3 090, 2 920, 2 840, 1 650, 1 600, 1 455, 1 330
10g	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	62	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ OS	3 140, 3 120, 3 000, 2 940, 2 840, 1 660, 1 605, 1 514

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N (as the case be) analyses.

**With the exception of compounds 8e and 10e which were crystallised from glacial acetic acid, all others were crystallised from ethanol.

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 8. ^dRef. 9. ^eRef. 10.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF PYRAZOLINES (11-15)*

Compd. no.	Ar	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Colour	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
11a	C ₆ H ₅	72	128 ^a	Light beige	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	3 330, 3 130, 3 040, 2 910, 2 845, 1 670-60, 1 600, 1 560, 1 385
11b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	77	125 ^b	Beige	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	3 375, 3 125, 3 020, 2 940, 1 660-40, 1 600, 1 480, 1 330
11c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	85	122 ^b	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	3 400, 3 140, 2 940, 2 845, 1 650, 1 630, 1 605, 1 510, 1 470
11d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	88	130 ^c	Yellowish green	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	3 340, 3 120, 2 940, 1 650, 1 600, 1 590, 1 510, 1 335
11e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	78	104 ^b	Light yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O	3 340, 3 120, 3 060, 2 900, 1 670, 2 650, 1 600, 1 400
11f	2-(C ₄ H ₉)S	82	195 ^b	Light brown	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ OS	3 420, 3 120, 3 000, 2 870, 1 760, 1 655, 1 590, 1 570, 1 480
12a	C ₆ H ₅	68	Oil	Brown	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	3 390, 3 120, 2 930, 1 608, 1 514
12b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	65	Oil	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	3 370, 3 120, 2 940, 1 660, 1 650, 1 514

(Table 2 contd.)

12c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	87	83 ^a	Colourless	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	3 345, 3 100, 2 960, 2 845, 1 655, 1 635, 1 605, 1 415
12d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	87	152 ^b	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 350, 3 100, 2 900, 2 850, 1 600, 1 590, 1 510, 1 340
12e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	84	110 ^b	Colourless	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ S	3 320, 3 100, 3 080, 2 920, 1 655, 1 645, 1 635, 1 430
12f	C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ - <i>p</i>	82	135 ^b	Reddish	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	3 380, 3 020, 2 720, 1 660, 1 650, 1 600, 1 515
13a	C ₆ H ₅	65	130-31 ^a	Cream	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	3 120, 3 100, 3 030, 2 950, 1 715, 1 640, 1 440
13b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	76	125 ^a	Light brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	3 090, 2 940, 2 840, 2 665, 1 640, 1 610, 1 510, 1 350
13c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	83	133 ^b	Yellowish brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	3 330, 3 100, 3 020, 2 960, 2 935, 2 840, 2 660, 2 640, 1 610, 1 510
13d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	86	134 ^b	Light brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	3 100, 2 840, 1 714, 1 670, 1 600, 1 530, 1 380
13e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	82	138 ^b	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	3 140, 3 100, 2 980, 1 650, 1 640, 1 620, 1 590, 1 480
13f	2-(C ₄ H ₉ S)	78	113 ^b	Brown	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 100, 3 090, 3 040, 2 980, 2 960, 1 670, 1 650, 1 620, 1 570, 1 530
14a	C ₆ H ₅	68	75 ^a	Pale brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	3 100, 3 125, 2 980, 2 863, 2 843, 2 780, 1 598, 1 475, 1 440
14b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	76	65 ^a	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	3 105, 2 958, 2 920, 2 758, 1 505, 1 476, 1 448
14c	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	79	Oily	Pale brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	3 100, 2 898, 2 940, 2 860, 2 816, 1 760, 1 570
14d	C ₆ H ₂ O ₂ CH ₂ -3,4	86	87 ^a	Pale brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	3 110, 3 000, 1 980, 1 900, 2 868, 2 790, 1 610, 1 488, 1 250
14e	2-(C ₄ H ₉ S)	65	Oily	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	3 120, 1 968, 2 930, 2 875, 2 845, 2 795, 1 565, 1 480, 1 440
15a	C ₆ H ₅	73	Oily	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ S	3 090, 3 040, 2 960, 2 870, 2 840, 2 798, 1 660, 1 605, 1 440
15b	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	88	85 ^a	Yellowish white	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	3 105, 2 958, 2 920, 2 858, 2 795, 1 475
15c	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	89	122 ^b	Pale red	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 010, 2 970, 2 910, 2 843, 2 798, 1 610, 1 514, 1 440
15d	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	89	150 ^b	Deep yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 080, 3 100, 3 010, 2 970, 2 858, 2 805, 7 605, 1 595, 1 510, 1 440
15e	C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	79	108 ^b	Colourless	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ S	3 100, 3 000, 2 960, 2 848, 1 440, 1 360
15f	C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ - <i>p</i>	88	120 ^b	Yellowish brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	3 100, 3 000, 2 980, 2 860, 2 810, 1 510, 1 440
15g	β-C ₁₀ H ₇	55	Oily	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	3 080, 2 988, 2 870, 2 840, 2 798, 1 660, 1 600, 1 440

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation : ^aMeOH, ^bEtOH, ^cAcOH.

98% hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent (Table 2).

5-Aryl-1-methyl-3-(2-furyl)-2-pyrazolines (14a-e) and 5-aryl-1-methyl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines (15a-g) from furyl chalcones (8a-c, f, g) and thienyl

chalcones (10a-g). *General procedure*: The compounds were prepared by the same procedure as described for that of pyrazolines 11 and 12 using methylhydrazine instead of hydrazine hydrate. The physical and ir spectral data are given in Table 2; 15e *m/z* (rel. int.) 176 (70%, M⁺), 241 (2%, M⁺-Cl), 165 (100%, M⁺-C₆H₄Cl) and 151 (22%, M⁺-C₇H₆Cl).

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRA OF SOME PYRAZOLINES

Compd. X no.	Ar	δ (CDCl ₃)
11e	O C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -p	3.7 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 3-3.5 (complex pattern, 4H, CH ₂ , CHR, NH), 6.5 (1H, m, furyl, C-3), 6.8 (1H, m, furyl C-4), 7.2 (1H, m, furyl, C-2), 7.3 (4H, m, ArH)
11d	O C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -p	2.95 (1H, dd, CH ₂ , A), 3.55 (1H, dd, CH ₂ , B), 5.65 (1H, t, CH-Ar), 6.5 (1H, m, furyl C-3), 6.6 (1H, d, NH), 7.5 (2H, m, furyl C-2, C-4), 7.6 (2H, d, ArH), 8.2 (2H, d, ArH)
11e	O C ₆ H ₄ Cl-p	2.7-3.6 (four doublets centered at 3.1, 3H, CH ₂ -Ar, NH), 4.8 (1H, t, CH-Ar), 6.4 (1H, m, furyl C-3), 6.5 (1H, d, NH), 7.2 (2H, d, ArH), 7.4 (2H, m, furyl C-2, C-4), 7.6 (2H, d, ArH)
11f	O C ₆ H ₄ S	3.2-4.0 (complex patten, 3H, CH ₂ , NH), 5.7 (1H, CH-Ar), 6.7-7.9 (complex pattern, 6H, thienyl, furyl)
12d	S C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -p	2.8-3.8 (four doublets centered at 3.5, 3H, CH ₂ , NH), 5.1 (1H, t, CH-Ar), 7.0 (1H, m, thienyl C-3), 7.3 (2H, m, thienyl C-2, C-4), 7.6 (2H, d, ArH), 8.2 (2H, d, ArH)

Results and Discussion

The key chalcones were obtained via the Claisen-Schmidt reaction⁴. Accordingly, condensation of 2-acetylfuran (7) or 2-acetylthiophene (9) with aromatic aldehydes in alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution gave the respective 1-(2-furyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (8a-g) or 1-(2-thienyl)-3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones (10a-f) (Table 1).

Conversion of the chalcones (8 and 10) to pyrazolines: The chalcones (8a-e, g and 10a-f) when reacted with one equiv. of hydrazine hydrate in ethanol, yielded the respective 5-aryl-3-(2-furyl)-2-pyrazolines (11a-f) and 5-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines (12a-f) (Table 2). ¹H-nmr spectra of 11c-e are recorded in Table 3.

The pyrazolines (11a-f and 12a-f) were characterized on the basis of their elemental and spectral data. Their ir spectra (Table 2) showed bands at 3 320-3 375 (NH), 1 640-1 670 (C=N) and 1 590-1 605 cm⁻¹ (C=C). ¹H nmr spectra of the pyrazolines 11c-f and 12d (Table 3) were found to be consistent with the assigned structures.

Furyl chalcones (8a-e, g) were also treated with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid as solvent. In this case, however, the products consisted of N-acetylated pyrazolines (13a-f) (Table 2).

The structures of the pyrazolines (13a-f) were deduced from their elemental and spectroscopic data. Their ir spectra showed bands at 1 650-1 715 (C=O), 1 640-1 670 (C=N) and 1 600-1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

The reactions of the chalcones (8a-c, f, g and 10a-g) with methylhydrazine in solvent ethanol were also investigated. The products obtained were shown by elemental and spectral analysis to be the N-methylated pyrazolines 14a-e and 15a-g, respectively (Table 2).

Scheme 1

Mechanism of reaction of chalcones with hydrazines: This mechanism can best be visualised as formulated in Scheme 1. Nucleophilic attack by hydrazine (or methylhydrazine) at the β -carbon of the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system forms species 16 in which the negative charge is mainly accommodated by the electronegative oxygen atom. Proton transfer from positive nitrogen to negative oxygen produces an intermediate enol which simultaneously ketonises to 17. Another intramolecular nucleophilic attack by the primary amino group of ketoamine 17 on its carbonyl carbon followed by proton transfer from nitrogen to oxygen leads ultimately to carbinalamine 18. The latter with a hydroxyl group and an amino group on the same carbon loses water easily to yield the end pyrazoline 6.

Scheme 2

In our view, the preceding mechanism seems preferable to another⁵ that involves 1,2-nucleophilic addition of hydrazine to the carbonyl group as a first step with the loss of water and nucleophilic cyclisation occurring in succession (Scheme 2).

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